

ESSENTIAL STYLISTIC AND LINGUISTIC ASPECTS OF TRANSLATING POLITICAL DISCOURSE

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Abstract: The investigation of several definitions of the term "political discourse" and the role of translation of them is the main focus of this article. Different categories of linguists and scientists are examined, and the characteristics of stylistic techniques and lexical units used in the translation of speeches by British politicians are explained. The linguistic awareness and worldview of contemporary society are shaped by political discourse. Political discourse encompasses all the elements that are present in the minds of both the writer and the reader and can impact speech generation and perception, such as previous texts, political beliefs and the political context.

Key words: Discourse, translation, political, speech, text, linguistic features

Examining the lexical and stylistic elements of political discourse translation is the study's goal. The following research techniques were applied in the work in accordance with the goals and purposes: structural, semantic, lexical, and stylistic analysis. Examples of speeches made by prominent British politicians were the study's source material, and these were found online. The fact that language and political communication are inextricably linked validates the work's importance. Furthermore, it might be claimed that politics is unique since it is primarily discursive in character, and many political actions are speech acts by definition. In several humanities fields, including linguistics, literary criticism, semiotics, sociology, philosophy, ethnology, and anthropology, the term "*discourse*" can be interpreted in several ways related to the study of language function. The idea of discourse has been used so frequently in modern linguistics that it has become somewhat ambiguous and has become used in an unorganized manner.

The global political discourse cannot be implemented without translation. Every participant in the conversation, who does not know the language, attempts to convey their ideas in this language by reflecting their political worldview, which is a component of their language worldview. This calls for a choice of communicative equivalents in a foreign language, which is really where translation starts. As a result, a participant in this kind of conversation serves as both the addresser and the addressee in addition to acting as a translator as best they can. As a result, when an addressee receives a communication in a foreign language, they translate it into their mother tongue. In the context of global communication, it is not feasible to assume that participants in a discourse will have adequate translation skills to translate political discourse texts accurately and to ensure consistency in the translation process. Particularly considering that machine translation techniques are becoming more accessible and are frequently mentioned by Internet users.

Regarding the linguistic interpretation of this idea, the discourse is described as "a speech work in the fullness of its expression (verbal-into national and paralinguistic) and

aspirations, taking into account all extralinguistic factors (social, cultural, psychological) essential for successful speech interaction" in the dictionary, which is a reference book of linguistic terms. Before moving straight into "political discourse," it is important to take into "politics": **science, art, field of activity, a special kind of social communication.**

In comparison to other forms of discourse, political discourse is a phenomenon that is far more common in society. Under this context, it is impossible to define the word "political discourse" with precision because, (1) there is no precise definition for the category of politics; and (2) political discourse cannot be distinguished from other types of speech based on a limited set of linguistic characteristics. Political speech is depicted as a complex of components that function as a single whole in a range of linguistic literature, representing political discourse as a diverse phenomena.

In all working languages, the translator must become proficient in the nuances of political speech. Political discourse encompasses all the elements that are present in the minds of both the writer and the reader and can impact speech generation and perception, such as previous texts, the author's political beliefs, and the political context. Furthermore, the primary lexical and stylistic elements of political discourse in translation can be identified using the speeches of British politicians as an example.

Politicians all around the world employ a range of linguistic strategies in their well-planned and pre-rehearsed public speeches to accomplish their objectives. Political speeches typically try to impose an ideological viewpoint on their listeners, shaping their perceptions of particular political realities. Although political discourse can foster goodwill among nations, it can also lead to disputes inside and between governments. Let's begin with repetition and parallel structures, which logically highlight the part of the sentence the speaker wants the audience to pay attention to, so creating an emotional impact. These kinds of constructs also help to create a distinct rhythm and balance the utterance, which facilitate easier listening.

There are various forms of repetition combined with parallel constructs in political discourse:

Language elements are repeated at the start of each construction (anaphora); at the end of each construction (epiphora); at the beginning and end of the structure (ring repeat); and at the beginning of the next construction (anadiplosis), an element that was encountered at the end of the previous construction is reused.

The following passage from British Foreign Secretary William Hague's address serves as an illustration of an anaphoric repetition: "*We have to re-balance our economy and deal with the legacy of national debt on a colossal scale.*" We need to expand into new markets, draw in investment, improve economic confidence, and close the trade deficit. Like many British firms, we too must rise to the challenge of making a livelihood in the globe. (Hague William) An example of a loop repetition is seen in the following snippet: That is the meaning of the country of opportunity. That is what it means to complete the task. (David Cameron) Anaphoric repeats, as is widely accepted, make a politician's speech more persuasive by establishing a background against which non-repeating material can be highlighted. Parceling is the next stylistic device that is typical of political speech. In order to connect with the audience and make the speech more comprehensible and convincing, the author uses packaged phrases. "*I went to that city after the Berlin Wall fell, and I will always remember it. The awareness that a vast continent was uniting.*" And when we buy new trains, we drive jobs

in Derby," says David Cameron. Chard conductor rail. The Warwick CCTV. Sleepers on the Boston Railway (UK Prime Minister Boris Johnson)

A rhetorical question is another stylistic device in political speech. This method heightens the listeners' receptivity, improves the impression, and sharpens their attention. The speeches by British politicians that are included below can all be regarded as having a strong emotional impact on the audience. The next stylistic device that British politicians employ in their speeches to give the remark a unique flavor is inversion. For instance: *"If I had been more quick-witted, I would have mentioned that Margaret Thatcher established the groundwork for the current prosperity of the city."* (John Boriss) It's also important to notice that a lot of new nouns that were created by compounding verb-adverb pairings have recently entered the vocabulary of English politicians. For example • take-over – Bosib olish • lay-out – ishidan ayrilgan odam • build-up – harbiy kuchlarni yig'moq

For example, President Obama notes that the United States economy had unparalleled expansion in the fifteen years that followed the 9/11 terrorist attacks, the most devastating event in the country's recent history. In response, President Trump poses as a supporter of the rights of this minority group by beginning his speech—which comes after a contentious election that was characterized by the dissent and protests of racial minorities—with a reference to the (presumably deliberate) choice of the moment for his discourse at the "conclusion of our celebration of Black History Month." Additional instances are President Trump's (presumptively personal) support for the defense of "the borders of other nations" during a period when the public was adamant about America's excessive military involvement in distant geographical areas, or President Obama's metaphorical reference to freedom "from the grip of foreign oil," presenting it as a pertinent result of his policies. From an informational perspective, students regarded this portion of the text evaluation to be both highly demanding and valuable. They had the chance to gain additional knowledge about American politics and political rulings. The challenge also stemmed from their prior views about American politics, society, and leaders, as these texts revealed the presidents' hands-on involvement in every aspect of their constituents' lives. After gaining a better understanding of the meaning of "truth versus lies" in political rhetoric, which is very different from the terms' everyday meanings in everyday speech, they were able to identify numerous passages in which the two speakers are observed maintaining this carefully calibrated balance between the two terms. The study's findings lead to the following conclusions: political discourse should not be understood in isolation from its background, author and audience expectations, and hidden agendas; political discourse should be understood in its entirety; one should not be restricted to linguistic moments when interpreting political discourse. Politicians are able to engage an audience with pertinent figures of speech and make a powerful impression through their mastery of rhetoric and lexical and stylistic devices. Political speech, then, shapes modern society's language consciousness and its linguistic image of the world. Linguistic form, political communication, and political thought are closely related.

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